

ON THE CONSTITUTION OF PEDICININ

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On the basis of available data, the structure of pedicinin (the pigment of *Didymocarpus pedicellata*), advanced by Sharma and Siddiqui, has been criticised. New facts concerning its nature have been brought to light and its character as a dibasic acid has been definitely established. Pedicinin undergoes reductive acetylation, and furnishes on catalytic hydrogenation an unstable yellow tetrahydro derivative which easily parts with two hydrogen atoms giving a stable red dihydropedicinin. Like the parent compound it forms a disodium salt. Evidences, both direct and circumstantial, have been adduced in support of a new formula for pedicinin, which is now regarded by the present authors as a chalcone quinone in preference to its earlier representation as 4:5:7-trihydroxy-6-methoxybenzalcoumaranone.

Siddiqui (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 703) isolated four crystalline constituents from the leaves of *Didymocarpus pedicellata* (N. O. Gesneraceæ). The results of a detailed investigation of these compounds have led Sharma and Siddiqui (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 1) to assign the following structures to them.

Pedicellin (I)

Pedicin (II)

IsoPedicin (III)

Pedicinin (IV)

The claims for the representation of pedicinin as 4:5:7-trihydroxy-6-methoxybenzalcoumaranone (IV) are based on the following experimental observations :

- (i) Benzaldehyde is produced by the action of alkali on pedicinin.
- (ii) Ferric chloride shows a colour reaction which is indicative of three unsymmetrical phenolic OH groups in pedicinin.
- (iii) Pedicellin (I), the constitution of which has been definitely established as 2:3:4:5:6-pentamethoxychalcone, yields an orange compound, m.p. 110°, by loss of three methyl groups on treatment with nitric acid in

glacial acetic acid solution. This substance, called methylpedicinin and represented by the structure (V), suffers further demethylation on short treatment with dilute alkali giving pedicinin (IV).

(iv) Treatment of pedicin with two atoms of bromine also leads to pedicinin, the formation of which is assumed to proceed *via* the intermediate chalkone dibromide (VI).

(v) Oxidation of pedicin (II) by potassium permanganate gives benzaldehyde as also pedicinin (IV).

(vi) Demethylation of pedicellin gives despedicellin (VII), which is also obtained from pedicin and pedicinin under identical experimental conditions.

(vii) Pedicinin furnishes a monoacetyl derivative and a monoammonium salt.

A close examination of the available data on the constitution of pedicinin convinced us that the arguments, put forward by Sharma and Siddiqui (*loc. cit.*) to explain the formation and reactions of pedicinin based on the structure (IV), are neither convincing nor conclusive. For instance, the spontaneous elimination of two bromine atoms of dibromopedicin (VI) as methyl bromide is an example of somewhat unusual occurrence. Moreover,

it is highly improbable that the double bond of pedicin, a chalcone derivative, would escape attack by permanganate and one of the hydrogen atoms attached to the unsaturated carbon atom of an ethylenic linkage would be involved in oxidation resulting in a coumaranone derivative (IV). It is also remarkable that out of the three phenolic OH groups present in pediciniu, only one would lend itself to acetylation and salt formation. The formation of despedicellin (VII) from pedicinin (IV) also appears improbable though not impossible. We, therefore, thought it desirable to re-investigate the constitution of pedicinin.

Pedicinin was isolated from *D. pedicellata* and was also prepared from pedicellin by the method of Sharma and Siddiqui. We substantiate Siddiqui's account of pedicinin as regards its molecular composition, melting point and other physical properties. Regarding its behaviour towards various reagents, we are not in entire agreement with the observations of Siddiqui *et al.* We have, for instance, observed that pedicinin is soluble in dilute potassium bicarbonate solution at room temperature. Pedicinin is, therefore, more acidic than what has been supposed. Siddiqui, moreover, reported the development of an 'immediate deep reddish brown' colour on treating pedicinin with ferric chloride in alcohol. Much significance has been attached to this test as indicative of three unsymmetrical OH groups in positions 4, 5 and 7 of formula (IV). We have not been able to observe any appreciable change of colour using dilute solutions of pedicinin (in alcohol) and the reagent.

The hydroxyl groups, as formulated in the proposed structure for pedicinin (IV), are in the *ortho-para* positions to one another. Consequently pedicinin should be expected to show strong reducing properties. Contrary to this expectation, pedicinin has been found to be stable towards alkaline *o*-dinitrobenzene (Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc., Sir P. C. Ray Birthday Vol.*, 1933, p. 65), chloropentamine cobaltichloride (Shibata and Hattori, *Acta Phytochim.*, 1930, 5, 117) and Fehling's solution, all of which are known to undergo reduction forming characteristic colouration or precipitates, as the case may be, in presence of polyhydroxybenzenes having *ortho-para* OH groups. These observations, taken in conjunction with the strong acidic character and deep colour of pedicinin, led us to suspect that pedicinin may after all be a quinone derivative and that there may be some truth in the statement of Price and Robinson (*Nature*, 1938, 142, 147). These authors had ventured the suggestion that the pigments of *Didymocarpus pedicellata* might be related to dunnione, the colouring matter of *Streptocarpus Dunnii*, Mast., in view of the fact that the genus *Didymocarpus* is closely related to *Streptocarpus* and the two series of pigments

occur as deposit on the leaves. The inability of Sharma and Siddiqui to support the idea of the English chemists seems to be justified inasmuch as the basic structure of the *Didymocarpus* pigments was proved to be different from that of dunnione. The possibility that pedicinin might be a quinone derivative was, however, not recognised by Sharma and Siddiqui.

We carried out some preliminary experiments in order to establish or disprove the quinone character of pedicinin and the results are given below :

(a) The colour of pedicinin disappears to a great extent on heating with aqueous sodium bisulphite solution but is restored by the addition of excess of alkali.

(b) An alcoholic solution of pedicinin turns yellow on warming with stannous chloride—hydrochloric acid.

(c) Pedicinin undergoes reductive acetylation with great ease forming a colourless acetyl derivative.

These observations imply that pedicinin is a quinone, and assuming a *para*-quinone structure, the pigment may be represented by the extended formula (VIII) or (IX).

(VIII)

(IX)

To decide between these two alternative expressions, pedicinin has been catalytically reduced. It smoothly absorbs *four* atoms of hydrogen giving rise to a yellow product, which rapidly turns red on exposure to atmosphere in solution. The red crystalline compound, isolated, from the solution melts at 134° and absorbs now only *two* atoms of hydrogen in presence of palladium-charcoal giving the foregoing yellow leuco-compound, which is unstable and is quickly converted into the original substance, m.p. 134° , by spontaneous aerial oxidation. These observations seem to justify our decision in favour of formula (IX), inasmuch as the alternative structure (VIII) should be normally expected to furnish a dihydro derivative. The yellow product is undoubtedly tetrahydropedicin having the formula (X) which is compatible with its instability ; and the red dehydrogenated

product is dihydropedicinin, which is apparently the quinone (XI). Pedicinin must consequently have one of the alternative structures (XII) or (XIII).

(XIII)

Reductive
 $\xrightarrow{\hspace{1.5cm}}$
 acetylation

(XIV)

Of these, compound (XIII) should be expected to behave like a dibasic acid (compare 2:5-dihydroxy-1:4-quinone and its derivatives) and form a disodium salt. In fact we have been able to prepare a disodium salt of pedicinin as also that of dihydropedicinin, m.p. 134°.

It has further been observed by us that dihydropedicellin, prepared by catalytic hydrogenation of pedicellin (I), gives on oxidation with nitric acid followed by hydrolysis of the product with alkali, the identical dihydropedicinin, m.p. 134°. The action of nitric acid on pedicinin is, therefore, a case not only of demethylation but also of oxidation, the chalcone group remaining intact. Analogous instances are by no means rare in chemical literature. Many alkyl ethers of tri- and tetra-hydroxybenzenes are known to undergo conversion into 1:4-quinones by the action of nitric acid. For example 1:2:4:5-tetramethoxybenzene is oxidised to 2:5-dimethoxyquinone

by nitric acid (Schüler, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1907, **243**, 281), which on careful hydrolysis by means of alkali furnishes 2:5-dihydroxyquinone having pronounced acidic character (Knoevenagel and Büchel, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 3993). The mechanism of formation of pedicinin from pedicellin is obviously very similar and may be represented thus :

Our results, therefore, go to show that the structure (XIII) may with confidence be advanced for pedicinin in preference to the earlier formula (IV), the inconsistency of which has already been commented upon.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Pedicinin and Pedicellin.—The method of Sharma and Siddiqui was generally followed. We found it, however, more expedient to separate pedicinin from the crude ether extract by washing it with very dilute alkali. For this purpose the diluted ether extract was taken in a vertical glass tube (75 cm. × 1.5 cm.), the tapered lower end of which had been closed by means of a piece of rubber tube and screw clip. A thin stream of 1% aqueous alkali was allowed to drop into the ethereal solution, when it dissolved the acidic constituents including pedicinin during its passage through the ether layer. The dark red aqueous solution was separated from the neutral ether extract, acidified with hydrochloric acid and kept in a cool place. The precipitate was collected after 24 hours, and freed from adhering oil by washing with petroleum ether. The crude pedicinin was washed with hot ethyl acetate and then repeatedly crystallised from chloroform.

The neutral ethereal extract was freed from the solvent on the water-bath under reduced pressure and kept in a refrigerator for 3 to 4 days when the major part of crude pedicellin crystallised out. This was twice crystallised from methyl alcohol, distilled in high vacuum (b.p. 150-55°/0.05 mm.)

and then crystallised repeatedly from ether. The transparent prisms or plates, thus obtained, melted at 93° * and did not depress the m.p. of a pure specimen of pedicellin, which had the same m.p.

Pedicinin formed carmine red needles, m.p. 203° (Siddiqui records m.p. 203°). (Found : C, 63.76 ; H, 4.3. $C_{18}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 64.00 ; H, 4.1 per cent).

Action of Nitric Acid on Pedicellin : Formation of Methylpedicinin (XV) and Pedicinin.—Methylpedicinin, m.p. 110° , was obtained as the main product by the method of Sharina and Siddiqui when the reaction with nitric acid was allowed to proceed for 40 to 50 seconds. If, on the other hand, the duration of the reaction was extended to 90 seconds, appreciable quantities of pedicinin were formed. Pedicinin was separated from methylpedicinin by taking advantage of the greater solubility of the latter in ethyl acetate. The identity of pedicinin, m.p. 202.5° , obtained directly from pedicellin, with the natural product was established in the usual manner.

Reductive Acetylation of Pedicinin : Formation of Tetraacetyldihydro-pedicinin (XIV).—Pedicinin (100 mg.), acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) and zinc dust (300 mg.) were heated on the water-bath for 2.5 minutes. The colour of the solution quickly deepened to reddish violet and then faded away to pale yellow. The yellow solution was filtered from the zinc dust, which was washed with glacial acetic acid. The combined filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure to a small volume and then poured into crushed ice. The yellow precipitate was collected and twice recrystallised from dilute methyl alcohol containing a little acetic acid when a colourless semi-crystalline product, m.p. 207.8° , was obtained. Attempts to obtain the compound in well-defined crystalline condition were fruitless. (Found : OMe, 6.62. $C_{24}H_{22}O_{10}$ requires OMe, 6.60 per cent). The acetyl compound is freely soluble in most organic solvents except petroleum ether.

Sodium Salt of Pedicinin.—Pedicinin (140 mg.) was dissolved in a small quantity of aqueous alcoholic sodium hydroxide by warming. To the dark red solution about 4 c.c. of 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide (free from carbonate) were added. The solution was then diluted with absolute alcohol till a slight turbidity appeared and allowed to stand at room temperature. A gelatinous precipitate soon appeared which changed into a brick-red granular mass on keeping overnight. This was collected and washed with absolute alcohol and ether ; yield 130 mg. (Found : Na, 12.88. $C_{18}H_{10}O_8Na_2$ requires Na, 13.37 per cent). The salt readily dissolves in cold water

* The m.p.'s recorded in this paper are uncorrected. Siddiqui reports m.p. 98° for pedicellin.

forming a red solution from which the original substance can be obtained by acidification with mineral acids.

Catalytic Reduction of Pedicinin : Formation of Tetra- and Di-hydropedicinin (X and XI).—Pedicinin (321 mg.), dissolved in alcohol (50 c.c.), was reduced by means of hydrogen in presence of palladium-charcoal (0.2 g. of 8%), which had been previously saturated with hydrogen. The absorption of hydrogen was very rapid. After 52 c.c. (calc. 53 c.c.) at 30° and 760 mm. had been taken up in course of 20 minutes, absorption practically stopped. The yellow solution was freed from the catalyst. During filtration the colour of the solution rapidly changed to deep red apparently due to aerial oxidation. The solution was concentrated under reduced pressure and cooled when dark rectangular plates were obtained. Purified by recrystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol it had m.p. 134° not raised by further crystallisations. (Found: C, 63.26; H, 5.0; OMe, 10.32. $C_{16}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 63.57; H, 4.63; OMe, 10.26 per cent). Yield almost quantitative.

Catalytic Reduction of Dihydropedicinin.—An alcoholic solution of the above compound (170 mg.) absorbed 14 c.c. of hydrogen (calc. 13.8 c.c., 2 atoms of H per molecule) at 27° and 760 mm. in presence of palladium-charcoal (0.1 g. of 8%). The red solution turned yellow after reduction and again became deep red on exposure to air as in the foregoing case. From the red solution dihydropedicinin (m.p. and undepressed mixed m.p. 134°) was isolated.

Dihydropedicellin.—Pedicellin (696 mg.) was hydrogenated using palladium-charcoal (0.2 g. of 8%) in alcohol medium. Nearly the theoretical quantity of hydrogen was taken up in course of 25 minutes. The oily residue, left after the removal of the catalyst and the solvent, was distilled at 135-45°/0.1 mm., when a colourless viscous oil was obtained. It could not be crystallised. Yield almost quantitative.

Oxidation of Dihydropedicellin to Dihydropedicinin (XI).—Dihydropedicellin (638 mg.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.), was treated with nitric acid (d 1.4, 0.3 c.c.) drop by drop. The red coloured solution was shaken thoroughly and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 90 seconds. Ice-cold water was then poured into the reaction mixture and it was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water till free from acid, dried over sodium sulphate and the ether removed. The orange-red, semi-solid residue was warmed with dilute alkali (15 c.c. of 5%) on the water-bath till a clear solution was obtained. The red alkaline solution was immediately cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The red precipitate was collected, washed with water, dried and twice crystallised from dilute

methyl alcohol as dark red shining plates, It melted at 134° and was found to be identical with dihydropedicinin, previously described, by direct comparison and by mixed m.p. method ; yield 60% calculated on the amount of pedicellin taken.

The *disodium* salt of dihydropedicinin was prepared by the method already described under the corresponding salt of pedicinin. In this case, however, no gel formation was noticed. Yield 300 mg. from 344 mg. of dihydropedicinin. The sodium salt formed orange-red feathery, glistening crystals having no m.p. below 300° . (Found: Na, 12.67. $C_{18}H_{12}O_8Na_2$ requires Na, 13.3 per cent).

All the specimens were dried at $100-10^{\circ}$ in vacuum over P_2O_5 before analyses, most of which were carried out by Mr. N. Ghosh, M.Sc. We offer our sincere thanks to Mr. Ghosh, as also to Dr. S. Siddiqui for the kind gift of a pure specimen of pedicellin.

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